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SOME ASPECTS OF RECONSTRUCTION OF ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT OF KNEE JOINT USING AUTOGRAFTS OF TENDONS M. SEMITENDINOSUS AND OF M. GRACILIS

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The study was performed in the Aversi Clinic.

Abstract. The main function of the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) ligament is to stabilize the knee joint. It connects the thighbone to the shinbone. It's most commonly torn during sports and physical activities that involve sudden stops and changes in direction — such as soccer, basketball, volleyball and tennis. It is very important to teach trainers and sportsmen how to prevent the occurrence of ACL damage, and how to treat it. In our work, we discuss the main symptoms of ACL dysfunction, the method of reconstruction of ACL using autografts of tendons m. semitendinosus and of m. gracilis and the rehabilitation issues after reconstruction. Our research is based on the experience collected during 50 ACL reconstructions performed in the Aversi Clinic starting from 2013 up to 2020. It turns out, that a timely surgical treatment appears to be the best prevention for further injuries of menisci and cartilage. The outcomes of surgery depend on the state of menisci and cartilage, the type of autograft, used for reconstruction, fixation material, the patient's age and weight, the mechanism of injury and, certainly, the qualification of the surgeon. Absolutely all 50 patients returned to the normal mode of life, which they had before the operation. Based on our experience we conclude, that the best time for surgery is 3-6 weeks after the injury, when the knee is completely extended and there isn't edema. For timely return to sport a full functionally controlled rehabilitation-recovery has a particular importance (in our case after 6-7 months). We did ACL reconstruction in age 40-50 for 3 patients: 2 ladies and 1 man. Indication for ACL reconstruction for ladies were very unstable knees. The indication for ACL reconstruction in man was high sports demand – wrestling coach. After surgery conditions of all 3 patients - improved significantly. Our recommendation is, that ACL Reconstruction in patients aged 40-50 years should be done in selected cases: when there are highly unstable knees in females or in high sports demands.

Keywords: Anterior Cruciate Ligament, Meniscus suture, ACL arthroscopic reconstruction, hamstrings, cartilage.